

A UNIVERSAL MODEL FOR PREDICTING THE EFFECTIVE SHEAR MODULUS OF TWO-DIMENSIONAL POROUS MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

A new method is proposed to predict the effective shear modulus of two-dimensional (2D) porous materials with large porosities, which is called the Large Porosity Model (LPM). The LPM can be used as a complement for the classic Three Phase Model (TPM), which is only valid when the porosity is relatively small. Through bridging the LPM and the classic TPM, a Universal Porosity Model (UPM) is developed. In order to assess the performance of the UPM, a series of representative volume elements (RVEs) of porous materials are constructed, with different volume ratios, shapes, and numbers of voids. By comparing the UPM predictions to the finite element simulation results, it is demonstrated that the UPM gives accurate predictions (relative error always less than 10%) of the shear modulus among the entire range of porosities (from 0% to 100%), for different Poisson ratios of the matrix materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

Porous materials have wide applications in architecture, automobile, aerospace, and other engineering structures. They mainly carry shear loads when used in structural components such as the core of metal sandwiched panels. Although several analytical models as well as numerical simulations have been carried out to study the shear modulus of porous materials, each of them is only valid for a small range of porosity. Moreover, the range of applicability of these methods has not been thoroughly investigated yet. To address this issue, we attempt to construct a universal analytical model to predict the effective shear modulus of 2D porous materials which covers the entire range of porosities.

2 THE LARGE POROSITY MODEL(LPM) FOR MATERIALS WITH LARGE POROSITIES

By considering the macroscopic shear strain as a result of deformations of many Euler-Bernoulli beams, we finally have the expression of the shear modulus of materials with large porosities as

$$\bar{G} = A \frac{E_m}{1 - \nu_m^2} (1 - c)^3, \quad (1)$$

where A is a constant independent of both the porosity c and the elastic properties of the matrix material.

3 THE UNIVERSAL MODEL TO BRIDGE TPM AND LPM

Three phase model proposed by Christensen gives a satisfactory prediction of effective shear modulus for small porosity materials. Given TPM underestimates the effective shear modulus while

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the LPM overestimates it, by bridging these two models, a Universal Porosity Model (UPM) which covers the entire range of porosity can be developed:

$$\begin{cases} \text{Small porosity} & (c = 0.0 \square 0.4): \text{TPM} \\ \text{Medium porosity} & (c = 0.4 \square 0.7): \bar{G} = \alpha \cdot \text{LPM}(c) + (1 - \alpha) \cdot \text{TPM}(c) \\ \text{Large porosity} & (c = 0.7 \square 1.0): \text{LPM} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

4 NUMERICAL MODELS TO ASSESS THE PERFORMANCE OF UPM

In order to assess the performance of the UPM developed in this paper, a series of numerical simulations for porous materials are carried out, with different volume ratios, shapes, and numbers of voids. A circular-void model for small porosities and a Voronoi-void model for large porosities are shown as below:

Figure 1: RVEs of two different void shape

We compare the predicted shear modulus by UPM to that of FEM, as well as other analytical models, and the results are plotted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The effective shear modulus of 2D porous material ($\nu_m = 0.5$) obtained by FEM and the predictions of the UPM and other theoretical models. The relative errors of the UPM predictions are shown by small circles.

We also repeat the numerical simulations by considering different values of Poisson ratio. It is shown that UPM always gives a satisfactory accuracy for the predicted shear modulus (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Comparison of FEM and UPM predictions for different Poisson ratios of matrix.

5 CONCLUSIONS

By bridging the TPM and the newly proposed UPM, a Universal Porosity Model (UPM) is proposed. A series of RVEs are constructed to assess the performance of the UPM. It is found that UPM developed in this study always gives a satisfactory prediction of the effective shear modulus of porous materials, for different Poisson ratios of the matrix materials, the relative error is always smaller than 10%, for the entire range of porosities (0%-100%)

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